

DRAGONS Science Quality Verification: A GMOS Imaging Example

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The first public release of the international Gemini Observatory's new Python-based data reduction platform, DRAGONS (Data Reduction for Astronomy from Gemini Observatory North and South), occurred late in 2019 and supports imaging for current facility instruments. Here we present an example of Gemini Multi-Object Spectrograph (GMOS) imaging and compare it with an equivalent Gemini IRAF reduction for the purpose of demonstrating similar photometric accuracy.

The reduction is done with both DRAGONS and IRAF in a standard way as described in the *DRAGONS GMOS tutorial* and the *Gemini IRAF GMOS imaging example*, computing the master bias and flat with the default parameters. Then the science images are processed and stacked. For the purpose of this comparison,

the stacking parameters are adjusted to use a similar method. IRAF's "imcoadd" uses a scaling according to the signal in the objects, so this was disabled (`fl_scale-`) to be consistent with DRAGONS. And to be consistent with a lack of sigma-clipping in imcoadd, the DRAGONS rejection thresholds were set conservatively (`hsigma` and `lsigma` parameters for the `stackFrames` primitive) to 20.

Sources are detected in both reduced images with DRAGONS's `detectSources` primitive, which uses SExtractor (the number of sources found is 1874 and 1925 for the DRAGONS and Gemini IRAF reduced versions, respectively). Magnitudes and a mean zero point are obtained by matching with the SDSS9 catalog. We remove sources without measured instrumental magnitudes or without reference magnitudes and sources

flagged by SExtractor. The sources that are saturated or that have more than 2% of their pixels that were flagged during the reduction are plotted with a star symbol below. Of the ~1900 sources detected in both DRAGONS and IRAF stacked images, we get ~250 sources with a reference magnitude (due to lack of catalog depth) and ~150 sources after removing the flagged ones.

More information on DRAGONS and Gemini IRAF can be found at <https://www.gemini.edu/observing/phase-iii/understanding-and-processing-data/Data-Processing-Software>. DRAGONS is an open source project *available* on GitHub with *documentation and tutorials on Read the Docs*. The international Gemini Observatory is a Program of NSF's NOIRLab.

Figure 1: Top panel plots the SExtractor calculated magnitude (using the MAG_AUTO parameter that uses an adaptively scaled aperture) versus the SDSS9 catalog reference magnitude. Bottom panel shows the magnitude difference, MAG_AUTO - REF_MAG. The sources represented with star symbols are saturated. The median of the differences with the reference magnitudes is at the level of 1.5% for both DRAGONS and IRAF.

Figure 2: Comparison of the images reduced with DRAGONS (left) and IRAF (right). The data for this comparison comes from the GN-2018A-LP-15 program. It consists of 9 exposures of 180 seconds in the r band. The under-illuminated horizontal stripes in the IRAF image, near the bright and saturated stars, are due to an effect present in the raw files, where saturated pixels would depress the whole amp in that row; this is virtually eliminated in DRAGONS by an overscan subtraction method that is more appropriate for the Hamamatsu detectors. ▼

